

Universal population dynamics with simplified spiking neurons

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Abstract

Despite the large plethora of different theoretical models of cortical circuits, the emerging neural dynamics is often similar. In this work we investigate to what extent the mean-field description of a neural population can be considered universal, i.e. partially independent on the specific single neuron model. We show this in the context of population density approach of network of Integrate-and-Fire neurons. We found that the source of this universality is in the strong analogies of the spectrum of the Fokker-Planck operator that governs the dynamics of the membrane potential density for different models. We show how it is possible to map on a quantitative level the firing rate dynamics of a population of uncoupled LIF neurons to that of VIF neurons, a simplified and analytically tractable model. Once the match is done also the Inter-Spike-Interval distribution of the two model are indistinguishable.

Introduction

Since its foundation the field of computational neuroscience is characterized by two different tensions regarding the models of biological neural networks. On one hand starting with the work of Hodgkin-Huxley on the detail mechanism of action potential emission, the emphasis is on biological detailed such as specific ionic channels effects. On the other simplified model of population of neurons have been used and proposed since the work of Wilson and Cowan. The idea behind the latter approach is that the computations that are behind all cognitive function are mainly due to emergent effects arising from the interaction of a large number of populations. In this context many authors have consistently use concept from theoretical physics, as mean-field theories, to derive population model from first principles. This allows to bridge the mesoscopic scale to the microscopic one and thus understand what are the key ingredients that must be considered and what is less important. A good example of the balance between simplicity and complexity is the population density approach in network of Integrate-and-Fire neurons. However during the years a plethora of different models has been proposed leaving open a question: to what extent the mean-field dynamics, i.e. the population dynamics, is universal and independent on the specific model used? The Exponential Integrate and Fire was show to be the best choice to fit the exact timing of spike emission in single neuron in-vitro, its non-linearity make the analysis essentially computational and very few analytic results can be obtained. If one is interested

however on the population firing rate it might be possible to obtain identical dynamics but using much simpler models. In this work we will show that is the case for uncoupled populations of neuron. We will study the simplified Virtual Integrate-and-Fire neuron and show how it is possible to use it to reproduce the firing rate of the "gold-standard" leaky IF. We demonstrate that the source of this universality is related to the model-independent structure of the spectrum of the Fokker-Planck operators which depends more on the boundary condition than on the single neuron details. We will also show how the same reasoning applies to the Inter-Spike-Interval distributions of the two models.

The results are presented as follow: we first present the general framework of population density approach of Integrate-and-Fire neurons. In particular we briefly review the spectral expansion of the Fokker-Planck equation for the population membrane potential and the equivalent formulation in terms of emission rate equations. Then we specialize the result to the Virtual Integrate Fire neuron a simplified model first introduce in [4]. We show the eigenvalues spectrum of the Fokker-Planck operator of the VIF and highlight its model-independent features by comparing it with the standard Leaky Integrate-and-Fire. We then comment on the complex relation between the first passage time distribution and the spectrum and show that the universality of the spectrum is reflected also in the universality of the the fist two moment of the Inter-Spike-Interval distribution of the two models. We also mention that despite its analytical tractability the VIF neuron is capable of reproducing true neural response function observed in vitro [1].

The mesoscopic parameter of the firing rate dynamics, i.e. the decay time and angular frequency, are studied as a function of the value of the reflecting boundary α and compared with the LIF model. Finally we show how a state dependent α allows to match quantitatively the rate dynamics of this two microscopically different models. We also show that once the identification of the parameter is done also the Inter-Spike-Interval distribution, I.S.I, are essentially indistinguishable.

Results

A simplified spiking neuron: spectral expansion

The general framework of Integrate-and-Fire neurons (IF) population dynamics is reviewed in this section with a particular accent to the spectral expansion of the Fokker-Planck equation and the emission rate equations. For notation and formalism will mainly follow [2], [3], [6].

Single IF neuron dynamics

The generic Integrate-and-Fire neuron (IF) is point-like neuron model and can be fully described by the following dynamics of its membrane potential $V(t)$:

$$\dot{V} = f(v) + \frac{I(V, t)}{C}, \quad (1)$$

where

1. C is the capacitance of the neurons' membrane (which will be omitted in the following, assuming the current to be measured in units of voltage/time);
2. $I(V, t) = I(t)$ is the driving current, that in general is assumed to be a stochastic spike train (will be given by the superposition of the spikes emitted by the pre-synaptic neurons connected to the target neuron).

3. $f(v)$ is the leakage term.

In this paper we will consider two choices for $f(v)$ correspond to the *leaky* and *virtual* IF neuron:

$$f(v) = \begin{cases} -\frac{v}{\tau} & \text{leaky IF} \\ -\beta & \text{linear IF} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The first is considered as the "standard-gold" of integrate-and-fire modeling, while the second is a version of the Gerstein Manderlbrot linear model, in which a key ingredient is introduced: a lower bound on the V values, acting as a reflecting barrier for the corresponding stochastic process. The VIF model was initially proposed for electronic VLSI implementations [4].

The synaptic current $I(t)$ is a spike train that can be well represented by an non-homogeneous Poisson process. In the neocortex the number of incoming spikes is usually very large while the each spike add a small contribution to the sum. In this condition, by the law of large number, we can apply a diffusion approximation and consider $I(t)$ as a gaussian variable with mean $\mu(t)$ and variance $\sigma^2(t)$.

Equation (1) which governs the dynamics of V is a stochastic differential equation, to which we can associate a probability density function (p.d.f.) $p(v, t)$ for V such that $p(v, t)dv$ is the probability that $V(t) \in (v, v + dv)$. A complete description of the stochastic process V will be then provided by the Fokker-Planck equation for the time evolution of $p(v, t)$:

$$\partial_t p(v, t) = \mathbf{L}p(v, t), \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{L} is the Fokker-Planck operator

$$\mathbf{L}(v, t) = -\partial_v(f(v) + \mu(v, t)) + \frac{1}{2}\partial_v^2\sigma^2(v, t), \quad (4)$$

generating the evolution of the p.d.f. of V . Introducing the probability flow $S_p(v, t)$ as

$$S_p(v, t) = (f(v) + \mu(v, t))p(v, t) - \frac{1}{2}\partial_v(\sigma^2(v, t)p(v, t)), \quad (5)$$

eq.3 is a continuity equation:

$$\partial_t p(v, t) = -\partial_v S_p(v, t). \quad (6)$$

The Fokker-Planck equation must be completed with the appropriate boundary conditions. For the IF neuron, the boundary conditions have to account for the emission of the spike (which is not generated by the dynamics eq. (3) of the system, but introduced as an *ad hoc* condition), the possibility of a lower bound v_{min} on the v values, and the enforcement of the normalization of the p.d.f. $p(v, t)$.

The first condition is expressed by the fact that any realization of the stochastic process $v(t)$ which happens to reach the threshold θ for the spike emission disappears", i.e. θ acts as an *absorbing barrier*. The spike emission rate, the fraction of realization crossing θ per unit time, is

$$\nu(t) = S_p(\theta, t) = -\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\partial_v p(v, t)|_{v=\theta}, \quad (7)$$

therefore the absorbing barrier condition must be

$$p(\theta, t) = 0. \quad (8)$$

Next, it must be taken into account that after spiking emission, v is brought to the reset potential H : each realization of the process v crossing the spike emission threshold

θ is rewound in H and there is no loss of realizations, i.e. $p(v, t)$ stays correctly normalized at any time. Therefore a condition must hold for the conservation of the flux S_p , such that the outgoing flux in θ is exactly compensated for by an extra flux at H :

$$\nu(t) = S_p(\theta, t) = S_p(H^+, t) - S_p(H^-, t), \quad (9)$$

where $S_p(H^\pm, t) = \lim_{v \rightarrow H^\pm} S_p(v, t)$.

Finally, a *reflecting barrier* α , possibly $\alpha \rightarrow -\infty$, implies that there is no flux crossing the lower bound v_{min} :

$$S_p(\alpha, t) = 0. \quad (10)$$

In the mean-field approach, the infinitesimal moments of the afferent current are expressed as function of $\nu(t)$ (7), now interpreted as the emission rate of presynaptic neurons:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(v, t) &= \mu[v, \nu(t)], \\ \sigma^2(v, t) &= \sigma^2[v, \nu(t)]. \end{aligned}$$

However, in the rest of the paper, we will focus on uncoupled populations in which the synaptic current is coming all from external sources i.e. μ and σ are constants.

State dependent spectral decomposition

The Fokker-Planck operator (4) has a set of eigenfunctions and associated eigenvalues,

$$\mathbf{L}|\phi_n\rangle = \lambda_n|\phi_n\rangle. \quad (11)$$

Introducing the inner product

$$\langle\psi|\phi\rangle = \int \psi(v, t)\phi(v, t)dv,$$

we can define the adjoint operator \mathbf{L}^+ by imposing

$$\langle\psi|\mathbf{L}\phi\rangle = \langle\mathbf{L}^+\psi|\phi\rangle, \quad (12)$$

which is the evolution operator for the backward Kolmogorov equation and it is given by

$$\mathbf{L}^+(v, t) = [f(v) + \mu(v, t)]\partial_v + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2(v, t)\partial_v^2, \quad (13)$$

It is possible to derive the general solution of

$$\mathbf{L}^\dagger|\psi_n\rangle = \lambda_n|\psi_n\rangle \quad (14)$$

Thanks to the completeness relation eq.(37), $p(v, t)$ can be expressed as

$$|p\rangle = \sum_n a_n|\phi_n\rangle, \quad (15)$$

where $a_n = \langle\psi_n|p\rangle$ are the time-dependent coefficients of the modal expansion and, since p is real, $a_n^* = a_{-n}$.

The dynamics of the a_n can be determined directly from the Fokker-Planck equation (3), ([7], [2]), in which is involved the ν dynamics and then, in order to create closed equations for the a , one needs a relation connecting $p(v, t)$ to ν . In the case of an uncoupled population the emission rate equation system (ERE) can be written as [3],

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\vec{a}} = \Lambda\vec{a} \\ \nu = \Phi + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{a}, \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where

- \vec{a} is the vector of the modal expansion coefficients with $n \neq 0$; 119

- the elements of \vec{f} are the flux over the absorbing barrier for nonstationary modes 120
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$$f_n = -\frac{1}{2}\partial_v\sigma^2\phi_n(v,t)|_{v=\theta} \quad \forall n \neq 0; \quad (17)$$

- Λ is a diagonal matrix whose elements are the eigenvalues of \mathbf{L} 122

$$\Lambda_{nm} = \lambda_n\delta_{nm} \quad \forall n, m \neq 0; \quad (18)$$

- $\Phi = \Phi(\nu)$ is the gain function (which binds the single neuron properties to the population dynamics) 123
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$$\Phi(\nu) = \Phi(\mu(v,\nu), \sigma^2(v,\nu)) = -\frac{1}{2}\partial_v\sigma^2\phi_0(v,t)|_{v=\theta}. \quad (19)$$

The eq.(16), in the mean-field approach, describes the collective behaviour of a pool of neurons in terms of the fraction of emitting neurons per unit time, $\nu(t)$, thus providing a dynamical formulation of the mean-field treatment, equally valid in stationary and transient regimes. The emission rate equation (16) has then explicit solution, 125
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$$\nu(t) = \Phi(\mu, \sigma^2) + \sum_n f_n a_n(0) e^{\lambda_n t}, \quad (20)$$

so that the spectrum of \mathbf{L} determines directly the characteristic times of the population dynamics. Furthermore, as $t \rightarrow \infty$, $\nu \rightarrow \Phi(\mu, \sigma^2)$, coherently with a negative real part of the eigenvalues. 129
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Infinite population of uncoupled VIF neurons 132

Because of its amenability to analytical treatment, we specialise the above analysis to the linear IF neuron (VIF), whose depolarisation is described by Eq.(1) taking as decay term $f(v) = -\beta$, a constant. For simplicity here we set $\mu(t) - \beta \rightarrow \mu(t)$, considering β as a constant inhibitory afferent current, and the corresponding Fokker-Planck operator L_{VIF} becomes 133
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$$L_{\text{VIF}}(v,t) = -\mu(t)\partial_v + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2(t)\partial_v^2. \quad (21)$$

Equation (11) is therefore a homogeneous second order differential equation with time dependent coefficients. From Eq.(12), the adjoint operator in this specific model is 138
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$$L_{\text{VIF}}^+ = \mu(t)\partial_v + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2(t)\partial_v^2, \quad (22)$$

The stationary solution, corresponding to $\lambda = 0$, turns out to be 140

$$\phi_0(v,t) = \begin{cases} -\frac{\nu}{\mu} \left(e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(v-\theta)} - 1 \right) & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ -\frac{\nu}{\mu} \left(e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} - e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}H} \right) e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} & \alpha \leq v < H, \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

where ν is the mean fraction of neurons crossing the threshold per unit time. By the Eq.(23), the explicit form of the gain function can be derived 141
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$$\Phi(\mu, \sigma) = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2}\partial_v\phi_0(v)|_{v=\theta} = \frac{2\mu^2}{\sigma^2 e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\alpha} \left(e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}H} - e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} \right) - 2\mu(\theta - H)}, \quad (24)$$

An analytic expression of the eigenfunctions ϕ, ψ that satisfies all the boundary condition is derived in the Appendix (using methods similar to [9]): in both cases, the eigenfunctions are combination of exponential functions, but with an explicit dependence on the L_{VIF} eigenvalues λ s. The latter are the solutions of the *characteristic equation*

$$\frac{e^\xi (\zeta \cosh(\zeta\alpha) - \xi \sinh(\zeta\alpha))}{\xi \sinh(\zeta - \zeta\alpha) + \zeta \cosh(\zeta - \zeta\alpha)} = 1 \quad (25)$$

where we introduce the variables $\xi = \frac{\mu}{\sigma^2}$ and ζ such that $\lambda = \frac{\sigma^2}{2}(\zeta^2 - \xi^2)$ and set for simplicity $\theta = 1$ and $H = 0$. This shows a convenient property of the VIF eigenvalues i.e. while λ is a function of both μ and σ^2 we can find a ζ , and so solve the spectrum, that depends only on one variable. This can be proven formally since we can derive a differential equation for the eigenvalue:

$$\mu \partial_\mu \lambda + \sigma^2 \partial_{\sigma^2} \lambda = \lambda$$

that admits a general solutions of the form :

$$\lambda = \mu k(\xi)$$

where $k(\xi)$ is an arbitrary function.

For the critical value $\mu = 0$ (already been identified in [3], where the VIF model was implemented with $\alpha = H$), the equation (25) can be solved and two family of eigenvalues are found:

$$\lambda_{DD} = -2\pi^2 \left(\frac{\sigma}{H - \theta} \right)^2 n^2, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (26)$$

$$\lambda_{ND} = -2\pi^2 \left(\frac{\sigma}{H + \theta - 2\alpha} \right)^2 n^2, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (27)$$

In general [3], [10], we can distinguish between two different kind of eigenvalues : (i) the *noise-dominated* eigenvalues λ_{ND} , those are present both in supra-threshold regime ($\mu > 0$ for the VIF) and in sub-threshold regime ($\mu < 0$ for the VIF), they are always real (ii) the other type of eigenvalues, are called *drift-dominated* λ_{DD} , their real part also goes as $-n^2$ but for a critical value for μ they bifurcate to complex conjugate pairs.

In the next section we will show the solutions of the characteristic equation as a function of μ and σ , and highlight the similarities of the spectrum between the LIF and the VIF.

Role of α : match with LIF neurons

In previous studies [3], [4], the reflecting barrier of the membrane potential was set equal to the reset potential $\alpha = H$. This choice simplifies the analytical study and was also natural for a VLSI implementation. The Leaky I.F. loses memory of the incoming stimuli at a rate of $1/\tau_m$ where τ_m is the membrane decay time. From a physical point of view the reflecting barrier of the VIF has the exact same role. In this case the memory of the neuron is related to the time to drive the depolarization below α which is θ/β in absence of afferent current. (!!!Nota: Mi ricordo che avevamo parlato di questa cosa ma non ricordo perchè l'ho scritta così che vuol dire below α forse intendevo to α ?)

On a population level the relevant time scales of the system are captured by the dominant eigenvalues of the F.P. operator i.e. $\tau_n = -1/\text{Re}(\lambda_n)$, so the effects of α of the spectrum induce different population dynamical regimes [5].

In figure (1) we show the spectrum of VIF operator for tree different values of α . As was pointed out in [5] and [10] when $\alpha = H$ all the eigenvalues will bifurcate from real to complex conjugates when the mean synaptic current is greater then a model-specific threshold $\mu > \mu^*$. This qualitative behaviour is universal, i.e. model independent, as it occurs in VIF, LIF and EIF ([10]).

When $\alpha \neq H$ two important features appear. First a newborn family of eigenvalues, called Noise-Dominated in [5], emerge. These λ will always be real independently on the value of μ .

The second important feature is that the Drift-Dominate family of eigenvalues still bifurcates to complex conjugate but we found that the value of μ^* where this occur depends non monotonically on both of α and the index of the mode n . Also this two characteristics appear to be universal as have been noted for the other I.F. models mentioned above. To be more precise all models show that in the large μ limit $Im(\lambda_n^{DD}) \rightarrow 2n\pi\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ where Φ is the gain function, while $Re(\lambda_n^{ND}) \rightarrow -\infty$. We also found that both for the VIF and LIF models the bifurcation threshold μ^* can be found by imposing $Re(Z_n(\mu, \sigma)) = 0$ where Z_n is the normalization coefficient of the adjoint eigenfunction ψ_n .

To summarize, it is reasonable to assume that the eigenvalue problem of the Fokker-Planck operator of I.F. neuron depend more strictly on the general structure of boundary conditions then on the specific drift component. For this reason the main features and hierarchy of the spectrum are universal.

Fig 1. Spectrum of the VIF neuron Fokker-Planck operator with varying $\alpha = H$. The dominant eigenvalues λ_n , found solving the characteristic equation (), are reported. The Drift-Dominate λ are in red tonality while the Noise-Dominated are in blue and the intensity of the tone differentiate the mode n . **A** $\alpha = H$ as in [3] only the DD eigenvalues are present and the all bifurcate simultaneously at $\xi^* = 0$. **B** $\alpha = H - 0.2\theta$ the ND family is now present even though the dominant modes are still DD. Moreover the complex conjugate λ_n will bifurcate at $\xi^* = \xi^*(\alpha, n)$. **C** $\alpha = H - 0.3\theta$ same feature of **B** but the dominant eigenmode is now ND up to a second bifurcation at high ξ .

Single-neuron features: ISI statistics, input-output gain function Φ and coefficient of variation c_v

The most important single-neuron features that rules part of the mean field population dynamics are the current-to-rate gain function Φ and Inter-Spike-Interval, ISI, distribution [11] for this reason we compare the distributions of first-passage time and its relation with the adjoint eigenfnctions $\psi_n(v)$ for the VIF and LIF neuron.

The p.d.f of the first passage time, $g(H, t)$, is always related to the backward Fokker-Planck equation [12] or in our notation $\partial_t g(x', t) = L^\dagger g(x', t)$. This can be solved in Laplace domain [4] :

$$\rho(x', s) = \int_0^\infty e^{-st} g(x', t) dt$$

were the problem becomes:

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \rho''(x, s) + b(x) \rho'(x, s) - s \rho(x, s) = 0 \quad (28)$$

with boundary condition

$$\rho(\theta, s) = 1 \quad \partial_{x'} \rho(x', s)|_{x'=\alpha} = 0$$

this has the same solution to the adjoint eigenfunction problem so for any I.F neuron it holds that the Laplace transform of the ISI density is:

$$\rho(s) = \frac{\psi(H, s)}{\psi(\theta, s)} = \frac{e^\xi (\zeta \cosh(\zeta \alpha) - \xi \sinh(\zeta \alpha))}{\xi \sinh(\zeta - \zeta \alpha) + \zeta \cosh(\zeta - \zeta \alpha)} \quad (29)$$

with the usual definition of $\zeta(s)$ and ξ .

As a consequence of this results it follows from (25), that the characteristic equation that determines the eigenvalues λ_n , of the F.P. operator, can be rewritten using the ISI transform:

$$\rho_{\theta, H}(\lambda_n) = 1 \quad (30)$$

this observation was made also made recently, with a different proof, also in [Bastian].

Equation (30) proves that a complex relation between the eigenvalues and moments of the ISI exists suggesting that a similarity on the structure of the spectrum might induce a similarity in the ISI distribution of two different I.F. models.

The mean of the variance of the ISI distribution can be computed from the Laplace transform:

$$\mu_T = \tau_{arp} - \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial s} |_{s=0} \quad \sigma_T^2 = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \rho}{\partial s^2} - \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial s} \right)^2 \right) |_{s=0}$$

where τ_{arp} is the absolute refractory period. From that the gain function $\Phi(\mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\mu_T}$ and the ISI coefficient of variation $c_v(\mu, \sigma) = \frac{\sigma_T}{\mu_T}$ are obtained.

In figure (2) we compare this two quantities in the plane (μ, σ) between a LIF neuron with $\alpha = -\infty$ and a VIF with $\alpha = H - 0.2\theta$. The effects of increasing further α in the VIF are mostly notable at relatively high σ but the general picture remain untouched.

The strong resemblance of this two key ingredients of the mean-field description of two microscopically different models suggests, once again, a possible mapping of (μ, σ, α) that can fit on a quantitative level the population dynamics of LIF neurons as we will show in the last section of the results.

Having a quantitative match of the firing rate dynamics of two different uncoupled populations is actually equivalent to say that the ISI distributions of the two are very

Fig 2. Comparison of gain function and ISI c_v . **A** The gain functions $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ of a LIF neuron $\alpha = -\infty$ and a VIF with $\alpha = H - 0.2\theta$ are compared. The only substantial difference between the two is a shift on the μ axis. **B** Shows the match of the c_v of the same two model

similar and viceversa. This statement can be proven rigorously for any I.F. model by considering the probability of emitting one spike in an interval $[t, t + dt]$ is given by $Pr(t_{spike} \in [t, t + dt]) = \rho(t)dt$.

Under renewal regime, which applies in the context of uncoupled population, the probability of emitting the m -th spike in the same interval, $Pr(t_{m-th spike} \in [t, t + dt]) = \rho_m(t)dt$ can be written as a convolution:

$$\rho_m(t) = \int_0^t \rho(t) \rho_{m-1}(t - \tau) d\tau$$

with $\rho_0(t) = \delta(t)$ and $\rho_1(t) = \rho(t)$. Then using the definition of the firing we can found a closed relation, in Laplace domain, between the ISI distribution and the the firing rate dynamics of a population of neurons that start all at $v = H$:

$$\nu_H(s) = \frac{\rho(s)}{1 - \rho(s)} \quad (31)$$

One could note that up to know we have showed an equivalence of only the first two moments of the ISI. However equation (31) implies that if a match of the firing rate dynamics $\nu_H(t)$ is possible, in particular of the transient, then the same holds for ρ . At the same time $\nu(t)$ is fully determined by the Fokker-Planck spectrum $\{\lambda_n\}$ which we have already showed to be in some sense "universal". In the next section we will show to what extent the relaxation dynamics of the two model, in different regimes, are qualitatively similar, before that we show yet another general relation between the c_v and the λ_n . By taking the limit $s \rightarrow 0$ it can be proved that:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\psi_k(H)}{\tau_m \lambda_k} = \frac{1 - c_v^2}{2} \quad (32)$$

Equation (32) is useful in different context. For example it clearly show that the first two moment of the the ISI constrain greatly the Fokker-Planck spectrum. In figure (3) we report the rate of convergence of (32) as a function of the number of eigenvalues included in noise and drift-dominated regime for the VIF, highlighting the fact that in the former case far fewer mode are necessary to reach convergence and so to capture the full dynamics of $\nu(t)$. The exact same behaviour was found in LIF neural population. Stated in more physical terms the firing rate dynamics is intrinsically higher dimensional in drift-dominated regime with respect to noise-dominated one.

Fig 3. Relation between the c_v and Fokker-Planck spectrum. The convergence of (32) is shown for Noise-Dominated **A** and Drift-Dominated **B** regime, as a function of the number of λ included. The former case need just few λ while for the second at least $n\lambda \sim 10^2$ is required.

Relaxation dynamics of the population: sub- and suprathreshold dynamics

The different eigenvalues of the F.P spectrum accounts for different time scales. Including all the eigenmodes up to m -th one allows us to describe accurately the firing rate dynamics $\nu(t)$ neglecting all the effects that live on a time scale $\tau \ll -1/Re(\lambda_m)$. The universal hierarchy of eigenvalues that we have shown above implies then a separation of time scales in the mean field description and the possibility of reducing the dynamics to a limited number of dimension [cit]. If one consider only the dominant eigen mode two possible scenario arise:

- $Im(\lambda_1) = 0$ which implies a one dimensional dynamics:

$$\dot{\nu} = \frac{\Phi(\nu) - \nu}{\tau_\nu}$$

- $Im(\lambda_1) \neq 0$ which implies a two dimensional dynamics:

$$\tau_\nu^2 \ddot{\nu} + 2\tau_\nu \dot{\nu} = (1 + \tau_\nu^2 \omega_\nu^2)(\Phi(\nu) - \nu)$$

where we defined the population decay time and angular frequency:

$$\tau_\nu(\mu, \sigma) = -1/Re(\lambda_1(\mu, \sigma)) \quad \omega(\mu, \sigma) = Im(\lambda_1(\mu, \sigma)) \quad (33)$$

so the firing rate dynamics of an uncoupled population is always a relaxation oscillator with state dependent coefficients. As already discussed in [...] the decay time and angular frequency are non monotonic function of the synaptic current. Figure (4) shows the match between theory and non linear fit of direct integration of Fokker-Planck equation of a VIF population.

In the literature a distinction is often made between sub-threshold regime ($\mu < \theta$) and supra-threshold regime ($\mu > \theta$). However the often related overdamped and oscillatory response regime can be found at various points of the plane (μ, σ) . Stated differently, just like in the LIF population, it is the nature of the dominant eigenvalue (being complex or real) that decide the type of response to a step stimulus. For example one can find over-damped response with a mean current well above threshold, and also a counter intuitive behavior of τ_ν as a function of the variance of the synaptic current.

Fig 4. Match between theory and Fokker-Planck integration. **A** the population decay τ_ν and angular frequency ω_ν as a function of the mean μ and standard deviation σ of the synaptic current measured in unit of threshold θ (τ_m is the membrane decay time). The contour levels and color function are the same used in figure (). **B** shows the match between theory (solid line) and non-linear fit of F.P. integration (dots) of τ_ν and ω_ν along the cyan cut reported in **A**. The same is shown in **C** for the magenta path. In this case an iso-firing rate curve was followed.

We now proceed to compare the decay time and angular frequency of VIF and LIF population. As reported in figure (5) the major difference, just like $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ and c_ν is a shift on the mean current (μ). This was expected also by analytical results on the spectrum obtained in both models. More specifically for the LIF we know that the bifurcation from real to complex conjugate will occur around $\mu = \frac{\theta - H}{2}$ while for the VIF this happens at $\mu = 0$. This is strictly true on the limit of $\alpha \rightarrow H$ where there are no Noise dominated eigenvalue for both models.

When $\alpha < H$, on one hand the bifurcation point mentioned above starts to be state dependent and on the other the noise-dominated family starts to play a role. In the LIF no matter the value of α , as long as it is different of H there will be a σ such that for any μ $\omega_\nu = 0$, i.e. the dominant eigenvalue is real. These two effects combined are responsible for the curvature of the $\omega_\nu = 0$ boundary as a function of α .

For the VIF instead there exist two threshold values of α : one below which the noise dominated eigenvalue is never dominant, yet the bifurcation of the drifted-dominated is state dependent and one above which the dominant λ is always real, i.e. $\omega_\nu(\mu, \sigma) = 0$ for all (μ, σ) . Moreover for relatively low level of σ the τ_ν of the VIF seems to be much faster than for the LIF.

Even when these differences are taken into account the overall picture still suggests remarkable similarities between two models that at a microscopic level are completely different.

Fig 5. Comparison of τ_ν and ω_ν . For three different value of α the comparison of decay time and population angular frequency is reported between the VIF (**A**) and the LIF (**B**). The best quantitative match between the two model is reached at not too low σ . However the qualitative change as function of α is consistent.

Can we map the VIF onto the LIF with a state-dependent α ?

The ERE formalism highlights a general structure of the dynamical laws of a mean field neural population which is independent on the specific IF neuron used. In the previous section we have shown that the parameters that govern the mean field dynamics are qualitatively similar for the VIF and LIF neuron. At the same time we also saw that this similarity is even stronger when we look at the first two moment of the ISI distribution as a function of the synaptic current.

In particular we note that some features of the LIF model not captured by the standard VIF can be taken into account by considering a non static $\alpha(\mu, \sigma)$. The idea of of state dependent threshold to model the emission of a spike is an old one and can also be justified with biophysical arguments.

We will not discuss here what are the characteristic of $\alpha(\mu, \sigma)$, and eventually $\theta(\mu, \sigma)$, that optimally implements the missing features of a static VIF but we will directly try to map the firing rate dynamics of a LIF population to that of a VIF.

To do so we first fix the stationary firing rate of the LIF ν_{LIF} and mean current μ_{LIF} then we found σ_{LIF} imposing:

$$\Phi^{LIF}(\mu_{LIF}, \sigma_{LIF}) = \nu_{LIF}$$

The ISI Laplace transform of the LIF is known to be:

$$\rho(s)_{LIF} = \frac{\sqrt{e^{Xr^2}} \mathcal{D}_{-s}(-\sqrt{2}Xr)}{\sqrt{e^{Xt^2}} \mathcal{D}_{-s}(-\sqrt{2}Xt)}$$

where $X_t = \frac{\theta - \mu}{\sigma}$, $X_r = \frac{H - \mu}{\sigma}$ and $\mathcal{D}_\nu(z)$ is the parabolic cylinder function solution of the Weber differential equation. From the analytical equation we then calculate the corresponding c_v^{LIF} . Finally, using standard find root algorithm, we search for the triplet (μ, σ, α) that satisfies:

$$\begin{cases} \Phi^{VIF}(\mu, \sigma, \alpha) = \nu_{LIF} \\ c_v^{VIF}(\mu, \sigma, \alpha) = c_v^{LIF} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

the system is under-determined so in principle infinite solution might exist. In figure we show the results of this mapping in both Noise- and Drift-Dominated regime. Once the mapping is done we integrate the Fokker-Planck equation of the two systems with the same initial condition i.e. $P(v, t = 0) = \delta(v - H)$. The firing rate dynamics, $\nu(t)$,

are indistinguishable despite the great difference of the whole stationary distribution especially in the ND regime, see figure (7). What is truly remarkable is the accordance during the all transient. This feature strongly advocate for the fact the ISI distribution of the two model must be very similar, a similarity that one cannot really understand by inspecting their analytical form. Another possibility, equally remarkable, is that to achieve this match one needs an equivalence of only the first two modes of the ISI distribution since the higher ones are not essential.

The PIF limit

When we go in the limit of $\alpha \rightarrow -\infty$ in (29) we recover the ISI distribution and hence the spectrum of the PIF neuron. This model was historically the first Integrate and fire model used to fit and explain the empirical data. In this case we have that

$$\rho(s) = e^{(\theta-H)\frac{\mu-\sqrt{\mu^2+2s\sigma^2}}{\sigma^2}}$$

that implies only complex eigenvalues. This raises an apparent inconsistency with what we discussed so far since we have shown that the higher is α the more real ND eigenvalues go close to $\lambda = 0$. This behaviour is also explicit in the analytical result (27) however we want to remark that having a dominant real part is a necessary but not a sufficient condition to govern the relaxation dynamics. The second requirement is that the the non stationary flux f_n of the mode considered has to be non-vanishing. As we show in figure (6), this is precisely what happen as a function of α . So in conclusion, for $\alpha \ll -1$ but finite, the dominant eigenmode will be real but due to the small flux it's effect can be neglected.

Fig 6. The dominant real eigenvalue **A** and associated flux **B** as a function of the reflecting barrier α here we set $\mu = \sigma^2 = 1$

Discussion

Mean-Field models of neural population, also refereed to as neural mass models, are at the core of modern computational neuroscience. Since the seminal work of Wilson and Cowan, the first phenomenological description of two interacting population, a great deal of work has been done in deriving these mean field description from first principles. In this context the framework of Integrate-and-Fire neurons and the related population density approach has established to be the preferred choice since in can be matched very well with experimental data despite it's relative simplicity.

If one is interested mainly in capturing the exact timing of spike emission and single neuron details the Exponential I.F. was shown to be the best choice [13]. However the non linearity of the model force the description of the mean-field dynamics to be computational [10].

In this work we showed that the firing rate dynamics $\nu(t)$ of two uncoupled population that are microscopically different, the VIF and the LIF neurons, can be mapped onto each other. In other words the mean field dynamics is for the greater part "universal".

We showed that the source of such universality is to be found on the general structure of the eigenvalues spectrum of the Fokker-Planck operator of the two models. In fact this structure is mainly governed by the set of boundary conditions that are the same for both models.

We also investigated how, for any I.F. model, the ISI distribution is related to the Fokker-Planck spectrum. The universal feature of the eigenvalues is followed by a strong similarity of the first two moment of the ISI which determine the two key element of the mean-field description, the gain function Φ and the ISI coefficient of variation c_v .

We gave particular attention to the role of the reflecting boundary condition located at α that was not well documented in the literature.

Using the ERE formalism we compared the population decay time and angular frequency to a step stimulus for both models and finally concluded that a state dependent $\alpha(\mu, \sigma)$ could be used to construct a map that relates the parameters of the LIF neuron to that of the VIF.

The optimal α can be found by imposing equivalence on the c_v and stationary rate of the two model. This can be done both in Drift and in Noise-dominated regime as we show in Results. In particular the stationary solutions to the Fokker-Planck equation are obviously different but the firing rate dynamics, even in the very fast transient is equivalent.

Despite the fact that eigenfunctions of the LIF are known analytically they are expressed as combination of confluent hypergeometric functions. This makes the analytical analysis difficult or even impossible except for limit cases. On a practical note instead, the derivation of the spectrum is for the same reasons challenging and requires high precision computation. This often leads to the impossibility of deriving a large number of eigenvalues often required in the context of power spectrum analysis. On the other hand, the VIF neuron is fully analytical, all the integrals involved in the analysis have closed form in term of exponentials. This not only opens the door to a better and deeper understanding of mean-field dynamics but also offer the possibility of fast and realistic simulations of large scale networks.

Thanks to mean-field universality that we studied here, we now know that this simplified model can reproduce on a quantitative level the firing rate dynamics of more complex models. For this reason we anticipate that the VIF neuron will be a powerful tool to tackle the current open problems in computational neuroscience.

Limitation and future work

Guided by the strong similarity of the spectrum we investigated here the universality of the mean field dynamics of uncoupled neural population. Real cortical columns are neither uncoupled nor infinite.

So a natural question arise: can we extend this results to overcome this limitation? In the framework of the ERE this amounts to ask whether or not the coupling coefficients:

$$C_{nm} = \langle \partial_\nu \psi_n | \phi_m \rangle$$

are qualitatively similar for different IF models. In a preliminary study we saw that this seems to be the case. The coupling coefficient have a major role in composing the transfer function that appear in the power spectrum analysis []. A quick comparison transfer functions of the two model studied here seems to hint in the same direction.

Moreover including more details in the models such as a synaptic delay distribution [] and spike frequency adaptation [] might even reduce the importance of single neuron details in the firing rate for power spectrum in favor of a more general structure.

All this observation and question will be analyzed in future work to test the true limit of the universal behavior that we reported here.

Regarding the finite-size limitation we can already say something. The Fokker-Planck equation can be extended to include finite size fluctuation [..] we found that even in strongly non linear (and coupled) regime the power spectrum of the population rate obtained in detailed simulation can be very well captured using a self consistent noise whose power spectrum can be derived analytically for any IF model:

$$|\eta(\omega)^2| = \frac{\nu_0}{N} \left(1 - \left| \frac{(i\omega + \nu_0)\rho(\omega) - \nu_0}{\nu_0\rho(\omega) + i\omega - \nu_0} \right|^2 \right) \quad (35)$$

where ν_0 is the stationary firing rate, N is the number of neuron in the population and ρ is the Laplace transform of the ISI. Since we have showed that the ISI distribution of the two models overlap then also the finite size fluctuations will be the same.

Supporting information

Propertiers and remarks on eigenvalues and eigenfunctions.

We now briefly list the main features and some results on eigenfunctions and eigenvalues, for more details see [6].

- Eq.(12) implies that eigenfuncios with different eigenvalues are orthogonal;
- for the completeness assumption of the eigenfunctions of the Fokker-Planck operator,

$$\mathbf{I} = \sum_n |\phi_n\rangle\langle\psi_n|, \quad (36)$$

both \mathbf{L} and \mathbf{L}^+ have tge same eigenvalues $\lambda_n = \tilde{\lambda}_n$ and, with an appropriate normalisation, the two sets of eigenfuncios are biorthonormal,

$$\langle\psi_n|\phi_m\rangle = \delta_{nm}; \quad (37)$$

- $\lambda_0 = 0$ is always an eigenvalue of \mathbf{L} and the corresponding eigenfunction ϕ_0 is the stationary solution of the population dynamics $\partial_t\phi_0 = 0$;
- The eigenvalues are in general complex with $\text{Re}[\lambda_n] \leq 0, \forall n \neq 0$;
- If λ_n is an eigenvalue, also λ_n^* is an eigenvalue, with eigenfunction $|\phi_n^*\rangle$ ($|\phi_n^*\rangle$), because \mathbf{L} (\mathbf{L}^+) is real. Setting $\lambda_n^* = \lambda_{-n}$, and consequently $|\phi_n^*\rangle = |\phi_{-n}\rangle$, the sums over the spectrum of the Fokker-Planck operator range over all the integers number;
- From the form of \mathbf{L}^+ and the boundary condition $\partial_v\psi_n(\alpha, t) = 0$, it can be seen that the eigenfunction ψ_0 must satisfy $\partial_v\psi_0 = 0 \forall v, t$, so ψ_0 is a constant. Because $\langle\psi_0|\phi_0\rangle = 1$ and $\phi_0(v)$ is a p.d.f., we have $\psi_0 = 1$. Finally, usin eq.(37):

$$\langle\psi_0|\phi_n\rangle = \int_\alpha^\theta \phi_n(v, t)dv = 0, \quad \forall n \neq 0. \quad (38)$$

From this result, it can be argued that only the stationary mode ϕ_0 contributes to the normalisation condition for $p(v, t)$.

The boundary condition of the Fokker-Planck equation are reflected on the eigenfunctions $\phi_n(v)$ while for ψ_n we have to assume: (i) ϕ_n, ψ_n to be continuous in the interval (α, θ) , including the possibility that $\alpha \rightarrow -\infty$; (ii) $\{\phi_n\}$ to be a complete set of eigenfunctions ; (iii) boundary conditions (8),(10),(9) must be satisfied by each $\phi_n(v, t)$. Then, the conditions on the eigenfunctions ψ_n of \mathbf{L}^+ result:

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_n(\theta, t)S_{\phi_n}(\theta, t) &= \psi_n(H, t)s_{\phi_n}(\theta, t), \\ \partial_v \psi_n(\alpha, t) &= 0, \\ \partial_v \psi_n(H^+, t) &= \partial_v \psi_n(H^-, t).\end{aligned}\tag{39}$$

The VIF stationary mode

Replacing the value $\lambda = 0$ in the equation (11):

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\partial_v^2\phi_0(v, t) - \mu\partial_v\phi_0(v, t) &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow\phi_0(v, t) &= k\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu}e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} + k'.\end{aligned}$$

To determine the constants k and k' , we have to take into account boundary conditions (8),(10),(9).

For the spectral expansion, ϕ_0 is supposed to be continuous in all the interval (α, θ) , but, because of the flux conservation (9), we expect a *jump discontinuity* in the first derivative of ϕ_0 calculated in H .

We thus suggest the solution in the form:

$$\phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} k_1\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu}e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} + k_2, & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ k_3\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu}e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} + k_4 & \alpha \leq v < H. \end{cases}$$

Making use of the boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}k_2 &= -k_1\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu}e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} \text{ from (8),} \\ k_4 &= 0 \text{ from (10),}\end{aligned}$$

while (9) is verified $\forall k_1, k_3$.

As ϕ_0 is supposed to be continuous, $\phi_0(H^+, t) = \phi_0(H^-, t)$, and then

$$k_3 = k_1(1 - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(\theta-H)}).$$

For now, our function is defined as

$$\phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} k_1\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu}(e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta}) & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ k_1\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu}(1 - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(\theta-H)})e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} & \alpha \leq v < H. \end{cases}$$

Since the eigenfunction associated to the eigenvalue $\lambda = 0$ is the stationary mode, it is a probability density function and the integral over (α, θ) has to be equal to 1. Imposing that condition, we obtain an expression for k_1 :

$$k_1 = \frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2} \left[\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu} e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\alpha} (e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(\theta-H)} - 1) - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} (\theta - H) \right]^{-1},$$

leading to an explicit form for $\phi_0(v, t)$:

$$\phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{c}(e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta}) & H \leq v \leq \theta, \\ \mathbf{c}(1 - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(\theta-H)})e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} & \alpha \leq v < H \end{cases}\tag{40}$$

where

$$\mathbf{c} = \left[\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu} e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\alpha} \left(e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(\theta-H)} - 1 \right) - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} (\theta - H) \right]^{-1}, \quad (41)$$

is the normalisation constant.

In the general case, the probability per unit time of crossing the threshold and re-entering into the reset potential H , is given by the flux of the realisations (i.e., the probability flux) at $v = \theta$:

$$\nu(t) = S_p(\theta, t) = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v p(v, t)|_{v=\theta},$$

where $p(v, t)$ is the probability density function of the depolarization process $V(t)$, and we used the fact that θ acts as an absorbing barrier.

The mean fraction of neurons crossing the threshold per unit time at time t is $\nu(t)$, and if the network state is stationary, is also the average emission frequency for any generic neuron.

If we consider a steady statistics of the input current and in a stationary regime, we have that $\nu(t) \equiv \nu$ is constant, and we can explicit it through direct calculation:

$$\begin{aligned} \nu \equiv \Phi(\mu, \theta) &= -\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v \phi(v)|_{\theta} = -\mu c e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} = \\ &= \frac{2\mu^2}{\sigma^2 e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\alpha} \left(e^{\frac{-2\mu}{\sigma^2}H} - e^{\frac{-2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} \right) - 2\mu(\theta - H)}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ is the gain function. In fact, in stationary conditions $\phi(\mu, \sigma^2)$ gives the output emission rate ν of the population and ϕ_0 is the constant p.d.f. $p(v)$ of the membrane potential at any time.

So we can re-write the stationary solution of the Fokker-Planck equation (3) using ν :

$$\phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} -\frac{\nu}{\mu} \left(e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(v-\theta)} - 1 \right) & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ -\frac{\nu}{\mu} \left(e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} - e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}H} \right) e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} & \alpha \leq v < H. \end{cases} \quad (42)$$

We now focus on a particular limit for the mean value of the input current, $\mu \rightarrow 0$, because, for the critical value $\mu = 0$, the uncoupled VIF network shows analytical properties useful to study the network behaviour [3].

Apparently the solution has a discontinuity, but it is a removable one: in fact, for $\mu \rightarrow 0$, the structure of the equation changes

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v^2 \phi_0(v, t) = 0 \Rightarrow \phi_0(v, t) = kv + k'.$$

With the same arguments of the previous case and imposing the above boundary conditions, the conservation of the probability flux and the normalisation, we get:

$$\lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} \phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{(H-\theta)(H-2\alpha+2\theta)} (v - \theta) & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ \frac{2}{H-2\alpha+2\theta} & \alpha \leq v < H. \end{cases} \quad (43)$$

Remarking that $\nu = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v \phi_0|_{v=\theta} = \frac{\sigma^2}{(H-\theta)(H-2\alpha+2\theta)}$, we can re-write the solution in the limit $\mu \rightarrow 0$ as:

$$\lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} = \begin{cases} -\frac{2\nu}{\sigma^2} (v - \theta) & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ -\frac{2\nu}{\sigma^2} (H - \theta) & \alpha \leq v < H. \end{cases} \quad (44)$$

We remind that the eigenfunction ψ_0 of the adjoint operator L_{VIF}^+ is

$$\psi_0 = 1.$$

Eigenfunctions of L_{VIF}

Taking $\lambda \neq 0$, the equation (11) becomes a homogeneous second order differential equation with time dependent coefficients:

$$\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\partial_v^2\phi(\lambda, v) - \mu\partial_v\phi(\lambda, v) - \lambda\phi(\lambda, v) = 0, \quad (45)$$

whose general solution is a linear combination of the two fundamentals functions

$$f_1(\lambda, v) = e^{(\xi+\zeta)\frac{v}{\theta}}, \bar{f}_1(\lambda, v) = e^{(\xi-\zeta)\frac{v}{\theta}}$$

where

$$\xi = \frac{\mu\theta}{\sigma^2}, \quad \zeta(\lambda) = \frac{\theta}{\sigma^2}\sqrt{\mu^2 + 2\lambda\sigma^2}, \quad (46)$$

and thus

$$\phi(\lambda, v) = c_1f_1(\lambda, v) + c_2\bar{f}_1(\lambda, v).$$

We put the dependence of λ in ϕ because of the presence of the function $\zeta(\lambda)$, which we will just call $\zeta = \zeta(\lambda)$ to ease the notation, in the definition of the fundamental functions, and we are not putting the explicit dependence on t because it is implicitly due to the presence of μ and σ^2 .

As in the stationary mode case, using the same arguments, we are looking for a solution in the form:

$$\phi(\lambda, v) = \begin{cases} c_1f_1(\lambda, v) + c_2\bar{f}_1(\lambda, v) & H < v \leq \theta \\ c_3f_1(\lambda, v) + c_4\bar{f}_1(\lambda, v) & \alpha \leq v < H \end{cases} \quad (47)$$

In order to simplify as much as possible the following derivations, we want to re-write the general solution as a linear combination of two *new* fundamental functions f_1, f_2 , where

$$f_2(\lambda, v) = k_1f_1(\lambda, v) + k_2\bar{f}_1(\lambda, v), \quad (48)$$

such that f_2 embodies the reflecting barrier, i.e:

$$S_{f_2}(\lambda, \alpha) = 0.$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_{f_2}(\lambda, \alpha) &= k_1\frac{\sigma^2}{2\theta}e^{(\xi+\zeta)\frac{\alpha}{\theta}}(\xi - \zeta) + k_2\frac{\sigma^2}{2\theta}e^{(\xi-\zeta)\frac{\alpha}{\theta}}(\xi + \zeta) = 0 \\ \implies k_2 &= -k_1\frac{\xi - \zeta}{\xi + \zeta}e^{2\frac{\alpha}{\theta}\zeta}. \end{aligned}$$

Using the arbitrariness of k_1 , we can fix it equal to 1, so that our *new* fundamentals solutions are:

$$f_1(\lambda, v) = e^{(\xi+\zeta)\frac{v}{\theta}}, \quad (49)$$

$$f_2(\lambda, v) = e^{(\xi+\zeta)\frac{v}{\theta}} + \frac{\zeta - \xi}{\zeta + \xi}e^{2\frac{\alpha}{\theta}\zeta}e^{(\xi-\zeta)\frac{v}{\theta}}. \quad (50)$$

In that way, by construction of f_2 , we suppose the solution of the equation (45) is of the form:

$$\phi(\lambda, v) = \begin{cases} a(\lambda)f_1(\lambda, v) + b(\lambda)f_2(\lambda, v) & H < v \leq \theta \\ d(\lambda)f_2(\lambda, v) & \alpha \leq v < H, \end{cases} \quad (51)$$

where we put the coefficients $a(\lambda), b(\lambda), d(\lambda)$ depending on λ since the presence of the $\zeta(\lambda)$ function.

Next we make use of the boundary conditions:

- Absorbing barrier $\phi(\lambda, \theta) = 0$

$$a(\lambda)f_1(\lambda, \theta) + b(\lambda)f_2(\lambda, \theta) = 0;$$

- Continuity condition $\phi(\lambda, H^+) = \phi(\lambda, H^-)$

$$a(\lambda)f_1(\lambda, H) + b(\lambda)f_2(\lambda, H) - d(\lambda)f_2(\lambda, H) = 0;$$

- Flux Conservation: Using the definition of the probability flow (5), then $S_\phi(\lambda, \theta) = S_\phi(\lambda, H^+) - S_\phi(\lambda, H^-)$ leads to:

$$a(\lambda)(f'_1(\lambda, H) - f'_1(\lambda, \theta)) + b(\lambda)(f'_2(\lambda, H) - f'_2(\lambda, \theta)) - d(\lambda)f'_2(\lambda, H) = 0.$$

We are denoting $\partial_v f_{1,2}(\lambda, v)$ as $f'_{1,2}(\lambda, v)$.

We have obtained the linear system:

$$\begin{cases} f_1(\lambda, \theta)a(\lambda) + f_2(\lambda, \theta)b(\lambda) = 0 \\ f_1(\lambda, H)a(\lambda) + f_2(\lambda, H)b(\lambda) - f_2(\lambda, H)d(\lambda) = 0 \\ (f'_1(\lambda, H) - f'_1(\lambda, \theta))a(\lambda) + (f'_2(\lambda, H) - f'_2(\lambda, \theta))b(\lambda) - f'_2(\lambda, H)d(\lambda) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (52)$$

and in order to have nonzero solutions, the determinant of the coefficients matrix must satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} \det \begin{pmatrix} f_1(\lambda, \theta) & f_2(\lambda, \theta) & 0 \\ f_1(\lambda, H) & f_2(\lambda, H) & -f_2(\lambda, H) \\ f'_1(\lambda, H) - f'_1(\lambda, \theta) & f'_2(\lambda, H) - f'_2(\lambda, \theta) & -f'_2(\lambda, H) \end{pmatrix} &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow f_2(\lambda, \theta)[f_1(\lambda, H)f'_2(\lambda, H) - f'_1(\lambda, H)f_2(\lambda, H)] + \\ -f_2(\lambda, H)[f_1(\lambda, \theta)f'_2(\lambda, \theta) - f'_1(\lambda, \theta)f_2(\lambda, \theta)] &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Recalling that the Wronskian of two functions $f_1(\lambda, v), f_2(\lambda, v)$ is defined as

$$\text{Wr}(f_1, f_2)(v) \equiv \text{Wr}(v) := \det \begin{pmatrix} f_1(\lambda, v) & f_2(\lambda, v) \\ f'_1(\lambda, v) & f'_2(\lambda, v) \end{pmatrix} = f_1(\lambda, v)f'_2(\lambda, v) - f'_1(\lambda, v)f_2(\lambda, v), \quad (53)$$

we finally obtain a *characteristic equation*

$$\frac{f_2(\lambda, \theta)}{\text{Wr}(\theta)} - \frac{f_2(\lambda, H)}{\text{Wr}(H)} = 0, \quad (54)$$

whose solutions are the eigenvalues of the Fokker-Planck operator L_{VIP} .

In order to find $a(\lambda), b(\lambda)$, fixing $d(\lambda)$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} a(\lambda) &= \frac{f_2(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta)}{f_1(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)}d(\lambda), \\ b(\lambda) &= -\frac{f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)}{f_1(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)}d(\lambda). \end{aligned}$$

Since eigenfunctions are unique up to some normalisation condition, we arbitrarily set $S_\phi(\lambda, \theta) = 1$.

Using the definition of the probability flow and the presence of the absorbing barrier in θ :

$$\begin{aligned} S_\phi(\lambda, \theta) &= [\mu\phi(\lambda, v) - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\partial_v\phi(\lambda, v)]_{v=\theta} = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2}\phi'(\lambda, \theta) = 1 \\ \Rightarrow a(\lambda)f'_1(\lambda, \theta) + b(\lambda)f'_2(\lambda, \theta) &= -\frac{2}{\sigma^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& d(\lambda)(f_1'(\lambda, \theta)f_2(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)f_2'(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)) = \\
& = -\frac{2}{\sigma^2}(f_1(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H))
\end{aligned}$$

Using the characteristic equation (54) :

$$\begin{aligned}
& d(\lambda)\text{Wr}(H)(-f_1(\lambda, \theta)f_2'(\lambda, \theta) + f_1'(\lambda, \theta)f_2(\lambda, \theta)) = \\
& = -\frac{2}{\sigma^2}(f_1(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)) \\
& \Rightarrow d(\lambda) = \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \frac{f_1(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)}{\text{Wr}(H)\text{Wr}(\theta)}
\end{aligned}$$

For this choice of $d(\lambda)$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
a(\lambda) &= \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \frac{f_2(\lambda, H)}{\text{Wr}(H)}, \\
b(\lambda) &= -\frac{2}{\sigma^2} \frac{f_1(\lambda, \theta)}{\text{Wr}(\theta)},
\end{aligned}$$

and we can finally write an expression for the eigenfunctions of the non-stationary modes ($n \neq 0$) (51) 478
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$$\phi(\lambda, v) = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \left[\frac{f_2(\lambda, H)}{\text{Wr}(H)} f_1(\lambda, v) - \frac{f_1(\lambda, \theta)}{\text{Wr}(\theta)} f_2(\lambda, v) \right] & H < v \leq \theta \\ \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \left[\frac{f_1(\lambda, H)}{\text{Wr}(H)} - \frac{f_1(\lambda, \theta)}{\text{Wr}(\theta)} \right] f_2(\lambda, v) & \alpha \leq v \leq H. \end{cases} \quad (55)$$

The dual eigenspace: eigenfunctions of L_{VIF}^+ operator. 480

Here we want to characterise the eigenfunctions $\psi(\lambda, v)$ of the adjoint operator (22). 481
Knowing the fundamental solution of (11) $f_i(v, \lambda)$ with $i = 1, 2$: 482

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} f_i'' - b(v)f_i' - (b'(v) + \lambda)f_i = 0$$

where ' denote the derivative respect of v and $b(v)$ is the total drift term, we can derive the equation for the Wroskian of the two fundamental solutions: $W(v) = f_1'f_2 - f_1f_2'$: 483
484

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} W(v)' - b(v)W(v) = 0$$

that has solution : $W(v) = e^{\frac{2}{\sigma^2} \int^v b(u)du}$. It can be shown by substitution that the fundamental solution of the adjoint eigenfunction problem:

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} g_i'' + b(v)g_i' - \lambda g_i = 0$$

are given by $g_i(v) = f_i(v, \lambda)/W(v)$, moreover if define f_2 to satisfy the reflecting boundary condition at α the adjoint eigenfunction is:

$$\psi(v, \lambda_n) = f_2(v, \lambda_n)/W(v)$$

The boundary condition for $\psi_n(v)$ are two:(i) $\psi_n(\theta) = \psi_n(H)$ that is precisely the characteristic equation found above and (ii) $\partial_v \psi_n(\alpha) = 0$ that it can be shown to be true if the characteristic equation is verified. If we set $\theta = 1$ and $H = 0$ we have the following expression for the normalized eigenfunctions:

$$\psi_n(v) = \frac{(\zeta + \xi)e^{v(\zeta - \xi) - 2\alpha\zeta}}{\zeta - \xi} + e^{-v(\zeta + \xi)}$$

$$\phi_n(v) = \frac{1}{Z_n} \begin{cases} e^{v(\xi-\zeta)} - e^{\zeta(v-2)+\xi v} & 0 < v < 1 \\ e^{\zeta(-v-2)+\xi v} (e^{2\zeta} + e^{\zeta+\xi} (e^{2\zeta v} - 1) - e^{2\zeta v}) & \alpha < v < 0 \end{cases} \quad (56)$$

For sake of brevity we omit the expression of the normalization coefficient $Z_n = \langle \psi_n | \phi_n \rangle$.

Acknowledgments

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Fig 7. Quantitative match of firing rate dynamics. The firing rate dynamics $\nu(t)$ and stationary solution of the Fokker-Planck integration of the VIF and LIF neural population are showed for Drift (**A**) and Noise (**B**) dominated regime. The parameter of the VIF are chosen to match the stationary firing rate and c_v of the LIF as described in the text.